

CO-DESIGN PARTICIPANTS DETAILS

ID	Gender	Location	Age
C1	Female	Tangkiling	NA
C2	Female	Tangkiling	47
C3	Female	Tangkiling	48
C4	Male	Tangkiling	49
C5	Female	Tangkiling	60
C6	Male	Tangkiling	NA
C7	Male	Tangkiling	NA
C8	Male	Tangkiling	58
C9	Male	Tangkiling	32
C10	Male	Tangkiling	37
C11	Female	Tangkiling	NA
C12	Male	Kalampangan	58
C13	Male	Kalampangan	57
C14	Male	Kalampangan	-
C15	Male	Kalampangan	-
C16	Female	Kalampangan	28
C17	Female	Kalampangan	49
C18	Male	Kalampangan	47
C19	Male	Kalampangan	40
C20	Male	Kalampangan	NA
C21	Female	Kalampangan	53
C22	Female	Kalampangan	50